

Developing mathematics teaching in ‘traditional’ instruction environments

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The international literature base offers a range of aspects that can fall within the remit of high quality mathematics teaching practices: the use of cognitively demanding tasks, the inclusion of openings for student reasoning, and working with multiple solution methods among these. The issue at the heart of this paper is whether these aspirations are universally practical. Located in a South African context where ‘traditional’ forms of instruction predominate, and where large classes and poor levels of resourcing are common, my focus is on the versions of ambitious practices that might need to be developed to be responsively useful: versions that would be recognizable as aspirations in the international field, and simultaneously agreed as useful and aspirational goals in such contexts. Strands of the Mediating Primary Mathematics framework, developed in South Africa, with staging points towards contextually sensitive, aspirational goals for ambitious teaching, are shared and discussed in the paper.

Setting the scene

In a recent review of frameworks considering the quality of mathematics teaching, Charalambous and Praetorius (2018) noted both the multiplicity of offerings in the field and differences in their points of focus. However, they also noted common elements, among these, attention to aspects of what Cohen (2011) has described as ‘ambitious instruction’. Many of these aspects are linked with the ‘reform’ agenda that is widely associated with the American National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) Standards (NCTM, 2000). Among these aspects are pedagogic practices involving the inclusion of high cognitive demand tasks that invite student reasoning (Stein, Smith, Henningsen, & Silver, 2000), encouraging students to work with multiple solution methods and explore each other’s explanations (McClain, 2002), with more limited emphasis on procedural working in mathematics in some frameworks (Charalambous & Litke, 2018).

These visions tend to be presented as ‘universal’. In this lecture I am not setting out to dispute the value of these practices. But my work in South Africa is located in a context at some distance from the conditions, culture and classroom norms of the American classroom settings that are the focus of NCTM-advocated practices. Primary level classrooms often have fifty or more children. In the last decade, national workbooks have been rolled out for literacy and numeracy, improving the level of access to texts, but student and teacher resources beyond these texts in terms of manipulatives continue to be limited. Only a small minority of high status schools have any technology available in classrooms; some ‘township’ schools have a usually rather dilapidated room with older computers that is infrequently used. Studies in primary mathematics education have identified substantial gaps in primary teachers’ mathematical knowledge (Venkat & Spaul, 2015) and problems with coherence, and limited

attention to connection and progression in mathematics teaching (Askew et al, 2019). Rote choral chanting of responses is a common classroom norm (Hoadley, 2018), and classroom culture in sub-Saharan Africa has been described as highly authoritarian in mode, reflecting aspects of broader societal cultures (Tabulawa, 2013). An emphasis on low level procedural working in instruction has been documented by the middle grades (Noor & Christensen, 2013). There is also evidence of limited success with trying to import reforms centred on learner-centred instructional practices.

My focus in this paper, and in the lecture that accompanies it, is to ask what this context and these conditions mean for what counts as ‘ambitious practice’ in primary mathematics instruction. Specifically, what might be viable and useful foci for developing the quality mathematics teaching in such contexts? And how do these foci overlap with and differ from what is seen as constituting high quality teaching in more advantaged settings?

Practical theory

The question about viable and useful foci for mathematics teaching development in traditional and authoritarian settings is an empirical one. But answering empirical questions involves assumptions about the world and human change within it, and therefore requires some leaning on theory. My position on teacher change is fundamentally a constructivist one: that development has to take into account teachers’ current knowledge bases and repertoires of practice, and build from these bases. Given the brief outline of context and conditions above, the list of ambitious practices derived from the international literature stands at a large distance from the existing state of play, making it difficult to achieve these lofty aims within the medium term.

A second aspect of interest in my work is finding levers with the potential to work for development at scale. This point is of importance in a South African education field in which smaller-scale qualitative studies abound (Deacon, Osman & Buchler, 2010), and where difficulties with moving to scale have also been described in the international literature (Maass et al., 2019). The implications for interventions seeking teacher development are to focus on mechanisms that are cost- and capacity-effective enough for moving beyond the confines and timelines of the research and development projects in which they were initially trialled.

Putting both of these imperatives together led us to the development of a framework for thinking about the development of primary mathematics teaching (the phase in focus of the work of the Wits Maths Connect-Primary project): the Mediating Primary Mathematics (MPM) framework (Venkat & Askew, 2018). The framework has a subject-specific and a rather ‘instructional’ bias, linked with the authoritarian, rather than dialogic, forms of teaching that predominate on the ground. Within instruction, staging points in terms of the mathematics that is offered for learning are built in a hierarchy that – at its base, involves teaching that displays some incoherence or error, into coherence, and then connection, and – at the top level – generality. Variation theory (Marton & Booth, 1997), elaborated with additional concepts developed by Watson and Mason (2005) and Watson and Mason (2006) is

built into key strands of the MPM framework to consider the example spaces worked with in instruction, with development work seeking to expand these example spaces.

Earlier writing details the framework itself (Venkat & Askew, 2018), ways of using the framework to evaluate teaching (Askew et al, 2019), and the ways in which generality as a goal fits within Vygotskian socio-cultural views of mathematics as a network of scientific concepts (Venkat & Adler, 2021). In this paper, I offer examples of the ways in which we have used strands of the MPM framework to consider episodes of teaching and then have conversations with teachers in traditional pedagogy settings, that take current practices into account and seek to build from them.

Strands of the MPM framework

The MPM framework breaks down attention to the incoherence > coherence > connection > generality trajectory across a number of strands built upon the tasks and example spaces related to tasks that teachers enact mathematical instruction upon. In line with the sociocultural framing and connected to the teacher-led instruction format, mediating between the student and the mathematics to be learned is seen as occurring via the teachers’ work with a range of mediating tools – artefacts, inscriptions and classroom talk/gesture, with the latter broken down further into three sub-strands related to the methods for generating and validating solutions, building mathematical connections and building responsive connections with student inputs and offers.

By way of example, in Figure 1 below, I detail the indicators for two of the strands in Tables 1 and 2 (from Venkat & Askew, 2018):

Table 1

Levels of artefact use, with indicators/illustrative excerpts

<i>No artefacts or artifacts that are problematic/inappropriate</i>	<i>Unstructured artifacts used in unstructured ways</i>	<i>Structured artefacts used in unstructured ways</i>	<i>Structured or unstructured artefacts used in structured ways</i>
0	1	2	3
Lesson is conducted purely orally, with no artifacts or inscriptions	Pairs of numbers adding to nine are explored and counters used to check that a pair of numbers totals to 9.	Abaci, 100 squares, etc., used with unit counting, and without reference to structural properties. Beads on the abacus used to add 4 and 8 by counting along 4 beads on the top row, 8 beads on the second row and counting all.	Abacus, 100 square/place value blocks/cards, number lines, etc. 10s strips and unit squares used to support identification of value of underlined digit in several 2-digit numbers.

Table 2*Levels of generating/validating solutions, with indicators/illustrative excerpts*

<i>No method or problematic generation/validation</i>	<i>Singular method/validation</i>	<i>Localized method/validation</i>	<i>Generalized method/validation</i>
0	1	2	3
Mixing of knowns and unknowns; error/ambiguity. Solution to $20 \div 4$ begins with the teacher talking about the need for five groups to share across.	Provides a method that generates/validates the immediate answer; enables learner to produce the answer in the immediate example space. Teacher tells learners to use counters to find the answer to $4 + 5$.	Provides a method that can generate/validate answers beyond the particular example space. Teacher shows how adding 10 on a 1–100 square involves moving one row down.	Provides/validates a strategy/ method that can be generalized to both other example spaces and without restriction to a particular artifact/inscription). Teacher works on adding 9 by adding 10 (as a quick fact) and then subtracting 1.

It is worth noting, in relation to the socio-cultural framing, that the trajectory goes from highly empirical ways of working with mathematics towards increasingly working with mathematics viewed as a connected network of scientific concepts in the Vygotskian sense. Seen through the lens of variation theory, this trajectory also embodies highly localised ways of working with mathematics in instruction at the lower reaches, to instruction that focuses attention on mathematical structure and properties. And layered upon these two theories, we found it useful – in the South African context – to consider the trajectory in relation to the incoherence > coherence > connection > generality path as it offered a development route that could be recognised as powerful and useable in a traditional pedagogy terrain.

In the following section, I offer extracts dealing with the ways in which teachers' ways of working with tasks and examples can be considered within particular strands of the MPM framework, and also the ways in which the model suggests responsive conversations with teachers that build on their current repertoires of practice in expansive ways. These excerpts are drawn from classroom observations in our broader research and development work in South Africa.

Analytical work coupled with developmental work

Excerpt 1

In an episode drawn from Venkat and Naidoo (2012), where a Grade 2 teacher had asked her class for a pair of numbers with a sum of 16, $8 + 8$ was the first student offer. The teacher responded by writing $8 + 8 =$ on the board, and then asked another student to check if

this was true by using bottle tops. This second student proceeded to arrange the bottle tops in two rows of eight bottle tops, and then counted the bottle tops one by one to get 16. The teacher wrote 16 in as the answer on the board, and then asked for other pairs of numbers that would give a sum of 16. $10 + 6$ was then offered, and written on the board by the teacher. Students were asked to check if this gave 16 by making the two addends on their individual abaci. Once again, following counting in ones, 16 was written in as the answer. $9 + 9$ was then offered. Once again, the same process was followed, with children asked to make the two numbers on their abaci, and count the total.

Analytically, we see here, the side-lining of attention to connections between examples. The result for $9 + 9$ is calculated empirically from scratch, rather than seen as connected with, or derivable from $8 + 8$. In fact, all the sums offered in this excerpt were calculated in this way, through repeated one-by-one counting. Of further interest is the mode of use of artefacts in this excerpt. No distinction is made between the use of bottle tops and working with abaci – both are used for counting in ones, and the arrangements of objects from one example are ‘cleared’ with subsequent examples starting again from scratch. The potential of artefacts such as abaci and the ‘doubles’ arrangement of the bottle tops to draw attention to number relationships that are useful for understanding number structure and properties, is – once again – negated in this kind of instruction. In coding terms, this excerpt suggests a Level 1 mode of working on both the ‘artefacts’ and ‘solutions’ strands.

In developmental terms, the coding at the level of a basic coherence leads to a focus on connection as a next step that is likely to be met with what Schweisfurth and Elliott (2019) term as ‘local receptivity’, as an aspiration well aligned with context and culture on the ground. One possible conversation here with a teacher might consist of discussing ways of ‘annotating’ the $8 + 8$ bottle tops arrangement to make $9 + 9$, rather than starting over, and adapting the first result to reflect this annotation. There are also other responsive pedagogic possibilities – asking about the children who were able to answer immediately without any overt counting, and whether there are responsive ways of working that might help to keep these students’ learning trajectories moving forward, rather than pulling them back into more rudimentary calculation strategies.

Excerpt 2

In a project working to develop the capacity of local district Subject Advisers to offer tailored mathematically oriented feedback, we observed a Grade 5 lesson on fractions in which a teacher began with some number lines drawn on the board – see Figure 1. She asked the students in her class to figure out the numbers of the unmarked tick marks on the lines. After a minute, asking the students to respond, she accepted chorused whole class responses for each number line. As one of the lesson observers, I noted that several children were able to offer appropriate answers, and noted also that on the 7 to 8 line, the chorused response tended to be: ‘*Seven, seven and one quarter, seven and two quarters, seven and three quarters, eight*’ – alongside the teacher gesturing to each tick mark along this line.

Figure 1

Teacher-drawn number lines on the board

Somewhat unusually, the teacher asked for explanations of how the children decided on what number to say. A few children put their hands up, and one offered: ‘*Three spaces, thirds; four spaces, quarters; five spaces, fifths*’ before trailing off. The teacher accepted this offer and repeated it, and then proceeded to move on to the next task.

Analytically, the artefacts ‘pre-prepared’ for use in this lesson are the number lines that have been inscribed on the board. The fraction number lines do have the potential to point to both ‘part-whole’ and ‘measure’ interpretations of fractions (Lamon, 2012), and the ways in which fractional parts are related to unit wholes. There are pointers to a Level 3 coding, with the caveat that all the examples drawn included a single unit gap between the start and end numbers on the number line, limiting the generality of the fraction-related thinking that children were invited to engage with. The example space on offer did produce a rationale with generality for the range of variation that was made available: that the fraction to count in should be linked to the number of intervals on the line. This solution method ‘holds’ for all cases with a single unit gap between start and end numbers with equally spaced intervals, and thus, has some ‘reach’ beyond the specific examples in this set. Broader generality is not solicited by the teacher; nor are the limitations of the reach of this rule broached or questioned: the rule is appropriate for the example space, but it remains localised to a particular category of fraction-oriented number lines.

Our conversation with the teacher in this instance was based on discussing the rule offered in this class, acknowledging its efficacy for the examples providing and noting that it encouraged the class to consider and verbalise how they produced their answers, and then asking about the rule in relation to a couple of additional examples – see below:

Figure 2

Additional examples

This conversation allowed for a focus, again, on teaching that allows for an expansion of current student understandings, while – once again – building from the teacher’s observed practice repertoire. Underlying this choice is Watson and Mason’s (2005) notion of finding

counter-examples, problems for which a given rule or property does ‘not’ work. However, the choice was not to frame the teacher conversation in this way, as this framing was likely to be more unfamiliar in a context where the teaching of low-level procedures for solving given sets of problems has been described as predominant (Ally & Christiansen, 2013). Instead, we offered and discussed an example that threatened the appropriateness of the rule, sensing that expanding the example space to include a more varied set of number ranges would be more likely to be incorporated into future practice. Other options are possible here too:

- What happens to the rule if there are unequal intervals?
- Can the problem be looked at if one or both of the number line bounds are rational numbers rather than integers?

Watson’s examples of questions that can be used to encourage children to attend to structure and generality are typically more open than the approaches we have tended to use, but the aspiration for development of pedagogy to encompass more opportunities for children to engage with mathematical thinking remains, in ways that are attuned to classroom conditions and pedagogic cultures in our ground.

Final Comments

Coming back to the question of whether visions of ‘ambitious instruction’ are universal, my sense is that this is not the most useful to ask. Rather, my interest is a more pragmatic one: can we set out a version of ambitious instruction that would, simultaneously, be recognised and seen as valid in the international field in mathematics education, while also being recognised as useful and reachable in staged ways in the local ground. An important point to note about the MPM model is that it is centred on mathematical expansion within pedagogy, rather than aiming for expansions in teachers’ pedagogic forms towards reform-oriented practices per se. For some reading our work, our ambitions may not feel ambitious enough. For us, the expansions we seek remain aspirational and practicable to work with on the ground, and at some scale. Askew et al (2019) have reported on improvement seen in the practices of a group of teachers over time in the context of our professional development intervention activity. In a context of high poverty, high inequality and low performance in mathematics, such evidence of moves towards making more expansive opportunities to learn mathematics available are important to take into account in a country where studies lamenting the lack of move towards learner-centred instruction abound. Essentially, our adapted versions of ambitious instruction, are – for now – sufficient to keep our hands full.

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